

**Work Plan for Madhesh University
Birgunj, Parsa, Madhesh Province, Nepal**

**A Work Plan Report Submitted for the
Candidature for the post of Dean at Faculty of Law and Public Administration**

Submitted to
**Office of the Registrar
Madhesh University
Birgunj, Parsa
Madhesh Province, Nepal**

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Executive Summary

This Report outlines the strategic initiatives and operational objectives of Madhesh University (MU) for the upcoming academic years. As the Dean, I will be committed to fostering an environment of academic excellence, innovation, and community engagement that aligns with the university's mission to provide quality education and contribute to the socio-economic development of Madhesh Province.

Key Objectives

1. **Curriculum Development:** Enhance academic offerings by introducing new programs, including a Master's Degree in Sustainable Humanitarian Action, Sustainable Project Management, Naturopathy and Health Care Professional, and Bachelor of Science in Medical Technology, Clinical Research, and Ayurvedic Medicinal Research. These programs will be developed in collaboration with relevant health councils and professional associations to ensure alignment with industry standards and community needs.
2. **Research and Innovation:** Prioritize research initiatives that address local and regional challenges. Establish partnerships with industry stakeholders to facilitate applied research projects, particularly in applied sciences and sustainable development through community engagement and impact statement.
3. **Student Engagement and Support:** Implement comprehensive support systems for students, including mentorship programs, career counseling, and skill development workshops, Student led social entrepreneurship aimed at enhancing employability and workforce readiness.
4. **Community Outreach:** Strengthen community engagement efforts through outreach programs that promote health awareness, education, and sustainable practices, in collaboration with local organizations to implement beneficial initiatives.
5. **Infrastructure Development:** Invest in upgrading facilities and resources to support academic and research goals, including enhancements to libraries, laboratories, and technological infrastructure.
6. **Quality Assurance:** Establish a robust quality assurance framework to continuously monitor and improve academic programs through regular assessments, feedback mechanisms, and accreditation processes, ensuring compliance with national and international educational standards.

Conclusion

Madhesh University is poised to make significant strides in the coming years, focusing on academic excellence, community service, and research innovation. By implementing this Work Plan, MU aims to position itself as a leading institution of higher learning in Madhesh Province, dedicated to nurturing skilled professionals and contributing to regional development. With the support of faculty, staff, and stakeholders, we are confident in our ability to achieve these objectives and fulfill our mission of fostering quality education and socio-economic advancement. The plan could be made more specific after knowing the institutional capacity, regulations and need analysis as it appears like vision paper.

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SECTION A

VISION AND COMMITMENT

It is with great enthusiasm that I present my vision and commitment for Madhesh University (MU) as I apply for the position of Dean. My aspiration is to lead MU in becoming a transformative educational institution that drives holistic societal change through education and community-based programs.

Vision for Madhesh University

Madhesh University is poised to be a beacon of hope and opportunity for the youth of our region. Education is a critical investment during this prime phase of life, and it is essential that we maximize the returns on this investment by equipping our students with the skills and knowledge necessary to thrive in an increasingly globalized world. Applied education stands out as a crucial area of study, particularly in Nepal, where there is a pressing demand for skilled manpower across various sectors, including national bureaucracy, defense, infrastructure, and social services. Our vision is to position MU not merely as an educational institution but as a catalyst for producing human capital that contributes to a prosperous Nepal and elevates the quality of life for all Nepal is. We aim to address the urgent need for effective technicians, managers, Entrepreneurs, lawyers, experts, and technical managers who can respond adeptly to the challenges of globalization.

Commitment for the Excellence

I am deeply committed to the mission of MU, which is to provide an educational environment that fosters knowledge acquisition, character building, and experiential learning. Our approach will emphasize the integration of formal and community based entrepreneurship education, reflecting the rich cultural diversity of our community and making education accessible and relevant to all learners.

To fulfill this commitment, we will focus on the following strategic initiatives:

- 1. Curriculum Development:** We will prioritize the development of a robust curriculum that meets the evolving needs of society and industry. This curriculum will be designed to be responsive to technological advancements and the dynamic nature of the job market.
- 2. Infrastructure and Resources:** With the recent initiation of land acquisition and infrastructure development, we will ensure that MU is equipped with state-of-the-art facilities that support innovative teaching and research activities.
- 3. Community Engagement:** We will actively engage with local communities to understand their needs and tailor our programs accordingly. This partnership will enhance the relevance of our educational offerings and promote social responsibility among our students.
- 4. Research and Innovation:** MU will foster a culture of research and innovation, encouraging faculty and students to engage in projects that address local and national challenges. This will not only enhance the academic reputation of the university but also contribute to sustainable development in the region.
- 5. Support for Diverse Learners:** Recognizing that many learners have been marginalized from mainstream education, we will implement inclusive strategies to attract and support these individuals, ensuring that education is accessible to all.

Addressing Future Challenges

In a rapidly changing world characterized by volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (VUCA), our graduates must be prepared to navigate challenges and seize opportunities. As Michel Dell noted, many jobs for 2030 have yet to be created, and we must equip our students with the skills and adaptability to thrive in this environment.

To achieve this, we will:

- Develop programs that emphasize entrepreneurship, sustainable management, and project-based learning, ensuring that our graduates are not just job seekers but innovators and leaders in their fields.
- Collaborate with industry partners to align our educational offerings with market demands, ensuring that our graduates are the first choice for employers.
- Create an ecosystem that supports continuous learning and professional development, enabling our graduates to remain competitive in their careers as mentorship program.

Madhesh University stands at a pivotal moment in its journey, and I am eager to contribute to its growth and success as Dean. Together, we can transform challenges into opportunities, develop human capital, and sustain our rich heritage while delivering quality education that meets the needs of our society. I humbly request your support in this historical endeavor to establish Madhesh University as a premier institution of higher learning, dedicated to producing skilled human resources that will drive the socio-economic development of our nation. Let us embark on this journey together to create a brighter future for all.

SECTION B

METHODOLOGY

This methodology outlined the structured approach for preparing the Work Plan Report for Madhesh University (MU). The report served as a strategic document that articulated the university's initiatives, operational objectives, and plans for enhancing educational quality and community engagement in the upcoming academic years.

Stakeholder Engagement

- a. **Identified Stakeholders:** Key stakeholders, including faculty members, administrative staff, students, community representatives, and industry partners were identified to contribute to the development of the Work Plan Report through informal discussion.
- b. **Web Site:** Web sites were visited and information's were gathered.

The basic source of information is given table 1 and 2.

Table 1: Basic Source of Information

Name of the Institution	Madhesh University
Address of the Institution	Birgunj, Parsa, Madhesh Province, Nepal
Telephone Number	+977 051-592292
E-mail Address	madheshuniversity.p2@gmail.com
Website	https://madheshuniversity.edu.np/
Date of Establishment	Bhadra 23, 2079 B.S/ September 8, 2022 A.D.
Type of Institution	State University
Funding Provision	Madhesh Province, Government

Table 2: Current Academic Programs Offered by the Institution

Level	Academic Programs	No. of Program
Bachelor's	BA.LLB and BPAM	2
Proposed Program	Bachelor's in Entrepreneurship (Social Learning Management Mode)	?

The information collection table for further analysis is given in annex which can be used for data collections for catchment area also along with above table 1& 2.

Reporting and Communication for Further Improvements

- a. **Draft the Work Plan Report:** Compile the findings, objectives, action plans, and evaluation strategies into a comprehensive Work Plan Report.
- b. **Review and Revise:** Circulate the draft report among stakeholders for review and feedback, making revisions as necessary to ensure clarity and alignment with stakeholder expectations.
- c. **Final Presentation:** Present the final Work Plan Report to university leadership and stakeholders, outlining the strategic initiatives and operational objectives for the upcoming academic years.

Actions for Improvements

- a. **Review Existing Documents:** Analyze existing university documents, including previous work plans, strategic plans, and performance reports, to identify strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement is limited to available information and informational information. It should be studied in depth.
- b. **Needs Assessment:** Conduct a needs assessment to identify gaps in current programs, resources,

and community engagement efforts. This may involve surveys, interviews, and focus groups with students, faculty, and community members.

- c. **Benchmarking:** Research best practices from other universities, both nationally and internationally, to identify successful strategies and models that can be adapted for MU as feasibility study.
- d. **Develop Action Plans:** Create detailed action plans for each objective, outlining specific initiatives, timelines, responsible parties, and required resources.
- e. **Prioritize Initiatives:** Prioritize initiatives based on their potential impact, feasibility, and alignment with the university's strategic goals.

SECTION C

UNDERSTANDING OF THE UNIVERSITY

Madhesh University (MU), established on Bhadra 23, 2079 B.S., stands as a beacon of higher education in Madhesh Province, dedicated to nurturing skilled manpower and fostering the comprehensive development of the nation. The university is rooted in the belief that quality education is the cornerstone of progress and aims to offer a diverse range of programs in arts, sciences, medicine, tourism, Ayurveda, law, management, education, oriental philosophy, technical fields, and various other disciplines.

The establishment of MU was propelled by a vision to create an educational environment characterized by excellence, integrity, and productivity. This vision was realized through the Madhesh University Act, enacted by the provincial assembly, which facilitated the establishment and operation of the university. Officially announced in the province's gazette on Baisakh 14, 2079, MU embarked on its mission to shape the future of countless students and contribute significantly to national progress.

As a national priority for the advancement of higher education, skill development, vocational education, research, and industrial growth in Nepal, MU aims to enhance the gross enrollment ratio in the technical higher education sector particular to Mahesh Province. The university seems to be operated under a blue ocean competitive strategy, targeting the unreached through innovative educational models that provide entry to all. This approach enables individuals from both formal and social learning management systems to acquire education and skills, particularly focusing on the informal sector and unorganized workforce.

MU is committed to offering bachelor's, master's, and doctoral programs in high-growth sectors, preparing youth for gainful employment through various specializations. The university's model incorporates best practices from Academic and skill development systems worldwide while respecting the national ethos and culture. It aims to act as the Provincial Skill Development Corporation, addressing industrial needs through action research and knowledge dissemination.

With a focus on creating a total quality human resource, MU will provide a comprehensive learning environment that promotes creativity, innovation, and entrepreneurship. The university is dedicated to establishing state-of-the-art facilities for education, vocational training, and skill development, serving as a center of excellence for research and development in education for socio-economic advancement.

MU will utilize modern governance and management processes to enhance learning, teaching, research, and socio-economic wealth creation. The university is committed to launching higher education programs in emerging areas, fostering collaborations with other higher education and research institutions both nationally and internationally.

To accommodate a diverse range of learners from various backgrounds, age groups, and socio-economic statuses, MU should gradually operate in partnership model, with a specific focus on establishing excellence at key locations province. The concept of a 'Virtual Campus' will facilitate collaboration among students, experienced faculty, and industry members, ensuring that curricula remain relevant to labor market requirements.

In summary, Madhesh University is poised to be a transformative institution that not only addresses the educational needs of the region but also contributes to the sustainable economic development of Nepal by focusing on self-employment and local technology promotion, ultimately overcoming challenges such as high foreign employment dependency and school dropout rates.

SECTION D

IMPLEMENTING UNIQUE PROVISIONS

In light of the transformative potential of the Indian Education Policy 2020, it is imperative for academicians at Madhesh University (MU) to advocate for the integration of technology and skill development within the educational framework. This integration not only aligns with national educational reforms but also addresses the pressing need for a skilled workforce in a rapidly changing global economy. Here are several compelling reasons and strategies to encourage the adoption of this approach:

Rationale for Integration of Technology and Skill Development

- 1. Meeting Industry Demands:** The integration of technology in education ensures that curricula are aligned with industry needs. By prioritizing Educational and skill-based education, MU can equip students with relevant competencies that enhance their employability. This alignment will help reduce the gap between education and the job market, ensuring that graduates are prepared to meet the challenges of a competitive workforce.
- b. Inclusive Access to Education:** By allowing flexible entry points for students from diverse educational backgrounds, including diploma holders and individuals from the informal sector, MU can foster inclusivity. Implementing cognition tests will help identify and support learners who may have been marginalized in traditional educational settings, thereby expanding access to quality education.
- c. Fostering Entrepreneurship:** The emphasis on entrepreneurship education will empower students to innovate and create their own business opportunities. By providing the necessary skills and knowledge, MU can cultivate a generation of entrepreneurs who contribute to local and national economies, ultimately driving sustainable development.
- d. Continuous Learning through Virtual Platforms:** Establishing a virtual campus will facilitate continuous learning and engagement with industry experts, academicians, and researchers. This model not only enhances the educational experience but also allows for the integration of real-world applications into the learning process, preparing students for practical challenges.
- e. Applied Research for Local Solutions:** MU can foster a culture of applied research that addresses local and national challenges. Collaborating with industries and professional bodies will promote technology development and transfer, ensuring that research outcomes are relevant and beneficial to the community.

Unique Provisions for Implementation

To effectively integrate technology and skill development, MU can consider the following unique provisions:

- 1. Blending Traditional and Modern Knowledge:** By integrating conventional knowledge from local craftsmen with modern technological advancements, MU can enhance local skills while promoting academic courses. This approach will not only preserve cultural heritage but also foster innovation.
- b. Centers of Excellence:** Establishing specialized centers for managerial, technology, and sustainable practices will facilitate research and innovation. These centers can serve as hubs for collaboration between academia and industry, driving technological advancements.

- c. **Lateral Entry and Dual Degrees:** Offering lateral entry into integrated master's programs and dual degrees across different disciplines will provide students with the flexibility to tailor their education to their career aspirations. This approach encourages interdisciplinary learning and broadens students' skill sets.
- d. **Lifelong Learning Opportunities:** MU should provide continuous training and education through various delivery models, including conventional, blended, and online education. This flexibility will accommodate diverse learning preferences and ensure that education remains relevant throughout individuals' careers.

Opportunities for the Excellence

Madhesh University (MU) has a unique opportunity to align its educational vision with the overarching goal of "Reaching the Unreached," particularly in the context of the Madhesh Province. This alignment can position MU as a leader in education and skill development, ultimately contributing to a prosperous Nepal. Here are several key opportunities for MU to consider:

1. **Inclusive Education Framework:** MU can develop an inclusive education framework that targets marginalized groups, including school dropouts and individuals from informal sectors. By implementing flexible entry points, such as cognition tests, MU can ensure that diverse learners have access to quality education. This approach not only fulfills the university's mission but also addresses the educational disparities.
2. **Focus on Vocational and Skill-Based Education:** With a strong emphasis on vocational education, MU can design programs that integrate industry needs with technological advancements. By offering competitive technological education that combines theoretical knowledge with practical applications, MU can produce skilled human capital that meets the demands of society and national development plans. This aligns with the policy's focus on enhancing skill development and employability.
3. **Entrepreneurship Development:** The emphasis on entrepreneurship education presents a significant opportunity for MU. By fostering a culture of innovation and problem-solving, the university can empower students to create their own business opportunities. This aligns with the National Policy's goal of promoting entrepreneurship as a means of economic development and self-reliance. It should enforce drastic improvements in culture for promoting industry.
4. **Establishment of Centers of Excellence:** MU can establish specialized Centers of Excellence in key areas such as agriculture technology, Pharmaceutical technology, and sustainable management practices. These centers would facilitate research and innovation, enabling students to engage in applied research that addresses local and national challenges. This initiative can enhance MU's reputation as a leader in technological advancement and contribute to the socio-economic development of the region.
5. **Virtual Campus and Continuous Learning:** The implementation of a virtual campus can facilitate continuous learning and engagement with industry experts, academicians, and researchers. This model allows for flexible learning opportunities, enabling students to access resources and support regardless of their geographic location. By leveraging technology, MU can enhance its educational offerings and ensure that students remain competitive in a rapidly changing job market.
6. **Collaboration with Industry:** MU has the opportunity to strengthen collaborations with industries and professional bodies from Mahesh and Tarai Areas, addressing the employment gap faced by fresh graduates. By appointing industry experts as adjunct faculty and involving

them in project evaluations, MU can provide students with practical insights and exposure to current industry practices. This collaboration will enhance the relevance of the curriculum and improve graduates' employability.

7. **Research and Development Initiatives:** Engaging in meaningful research and development activities will allow MU to explore innovative technologies that improve productivity and income for enterprises in the tarai areas of Nepal. By focusing on applied research that addresses real-world challenges, MU can contribute to national development and position itself as a key player in technological innovation.
8. **Lifelong Learning and Continuous Training:** MU can create pathways for lifelong learning by offering continuous training and education through various delivery models, including conventional, blended, and online education for preparing skill labour by transferring skills from foreign returnee workers. This flexibility will accommodate diverse learning preferences and ensure that education remains relevant throughout individuals' careers.

Conclusion of the Section

Madhesh University stands at a crucial juncture where the integration of education, culture and skill development can significantly enhance its educational offerings and societal impact. By embracing these opportunities will not only fulfill the university's vision of "Reaching the Unreached" but also contribute to a prosperous and self-sufficient Madhesh, MU can empower youth, reduce dependency on foreign employment, and promote local technologies. Academicians play a vital role in advocating for these changes, ensuring that MU not only meets the educational needs of its students but also contributes to the socio-economic development of Madhesh Province and Nepal as a whole.

SECTION E

ACADEMIC EXCELLENCE PLAN FOR MADHESH UNIVERSITY

As the Dean of Madhesh University (MU), my plan for achieving academic excellence will focus on establishing a robust framework that aligns with the university's mission and objectives. This plan will encompass the following key areas:

Curriculum Development and Innovation

- Develop a diverse range of industry-relevant courses in fields such as art, science, medicine, tourism, Ayurveda, law, management, education, oriental philosophy, and technical subjects
- Incorporate life-skill and livelihood-based courses through culture-friendly pedagogy
- Collaborate with industry experts and international universities to design cutting-edge curricula

Proposed Bachelor Programs

Madhesh University aims to enhance its academic offerings by introducing three specialized Bachelor programs in collaboration with relevant health councils and professional associations. These programs will focus on equipping students with the necessary skills and knowledge to excel in their respective fields.

1. Bachelor of Science in Clinical Research

Collaboration: Health Professional Council Nepal

Program Overview

The Bachelor of Science in Clinical Research will prepare students for careers in clinical trials, research methodologies, and regulatory affairs. The program will cover essential topics such as:

- Principles of Clinical Research
- Biostatistics and Data Management
- Ethical Considerations in Research
- Clinical Trial Design and Management
- Regulatory Affairs and Compliance

Career Opportunities

Graduates can pursue careers as clinical research associates, data managers, regulatory affairs specialists, or clinical trial coordinators in hospitals, pharmaceutical companies, and research organizations.

2. Bachelor of Science in Ayurvedic Medicinal Research

Collaboration: Ayurvedic Council and Professional Associations

Program Overview: This program will focus on the scientific study of Ayurvedic principles and practices. Key courses will include:

- Fundamentals of Ayurveda
- Herbal Medicine and Pharmacognosy
- Ayurvedic Diagnostics and Treatments
- Research Methodologies in Ayurveda
- Integrative Medicine Approaches

Career Opportunities

Graduates will be qualified to work as Ayurvedic practitioners, researchers in herbal medicine, consultants in wellness centers, or educators in Ayurvedic studies.

3. Bachelor of Science in Medical Technology

Collaboration: Nepal Health Professional Council (NHPC), Nepal Medical Council (NMC), and Nepal Engineering Council (NEC)

Program Overview: The Bachelor of Science in Medical Technology will prepare students for roles in laboratory and diagnostic services. The curriculum will include:

- Fundamentals of Medical Technology
- Laboratory Techniques and Instrumentation
- Quality Assurance in Laboratory Services
- Clinical Biochemistry and Microbiology
- Health Informatics and Data Management

Career Opportunities

Graduates can work as medical technologists, laboratory managers, quality control analysts, or health informatics specialists in hospitals, diagnostic laboratories, and research institutions.

Admission Requirements

Completion of higher secondary education (10+2) in Science with Physics, Chemistry, and Biology, Diploma in Nursing, Health Assistant

Proposed Master's Programs

1. Master's Degree in Sustainable Humanitarian Action

Madhesh University should introduce a groundbreaking Master's Degree in Sustainable Humanitarian Action, designed to empower future humanitarian leaders with the knowledge and skills to tackle global challenges through sustainable and innovative approaches.

Program Overview

- Delivery: Blended learning (physical and online classes, practical internships, conferences, and study visits)

Objectives:

- Obtain key concepts and practical knowledge in sustainable humanitarian action
- Acquire a sustainable mindset to deliver impactful projects
- Attain critical humanitarian management and leadership skills

Curriculum

- The curriculum covers a wide range of topics, including:
- Introduction to humanitarian action and global citizenship
- Sustainable humanitarian mindset and economy
- International humanitarian organizations, law, and ethics
- Leveraging technology and innovation in the humanitarian field
- Humanitarian diplomacy, peacemaking, and soft power

- Leadership and etiquette in the humanitarian sector
- Foresight, strategies, and planning for the future of humanitarianism
- English proficiency
- Community Development
- Disaster Management
- Boarder Issues

Career Opportunities

Graduates of the Master's Degree in Sustainable Humanitarian Action will be equipped to pursue diverse career paths in the humanitarian sector, such as:

- Project/program officers, managers, and directors in NGOs and international organizations
- Consultants and advisors in humanitarian foundations and charities
- Academics and researchers in humanitarian studies
- Corporate social responsibility (CSR) professionals in the private sector
- Admission Requirements
- Bachelor's degree with a minimum second division
- Relevant work experience or volunteer hours in the humanitarian field will be given priority
- Curriculum vitae, statement of purpose, and two reference letters

2. Master's Degree in Sustainable Project Management

Madhesh University is set to launch a Master's Degree in Sustainable Project Management, designed to equip students with the skills and knowledge necessary to lead and manage projects that promote sustainability across various sectors. The program will be structured over four semesters, focusing on a blend of common courses, research, and specialized electives.

Program Structure

Semester 1: Common Courses

The first semester will lay the foundation for all students, covering essential topics in project management and sustainability. Core courses will include:

- **Principles of Project Management:** Introduction to project management methodologies, tools, and techniques.
- **Sustainable Development and Project Management:** Understanding the principles of sustainability and their application in project management.
- **Contract and Procurement Management:** Techniques for conducting procurement and contract management.
- **Ethics and Person ability Development in Project Management:** Exploring ethical considerations and responsibilities in managing projects with personality development.
- **Organization Management:** Exploring the organizational practices

Semester 2: Research-Focused

The second semester will emphasize research skills and methodologies, allowing students to develop their research proposals and conduct preliminary research. Courses will include:

- **Advanced Research Methods:** In-depth exploration of research design, data collection, and analysis.

- **Sustainability Assessment:** Techniques for assessing the sustainability of projects and their impacts on communities and environments.
- **Capstone Project Development:** Guidance on developing a comprehensive capstone project that addresses a real-world sustainability challenge.
- **Project Development policy:** In-depth exploration of framework and policy.

Semester 3: Electives Based on Bachelor Entry Focus

In the third semester, students will choose electives tailored to their undergraduate backgrounds and career interests. Elective options will include:

- **IT Projects:** Managing technology-driven projects, focusing on software development and IT infrastructure.
- **Hospital Projects:** Project management in healthcare settings, including facility management and health program implementation.
- **Construction Projects:** Sustainable practices in construction project management, including green building techniques.
- **Community Development Projects:** Strategies for managing projects that aim to improve community welfare and development.
- **Educational Projects:** Project management in educational settings, focusing on curriculum development and educational program implementation.

Semester 4: Practical Application and Thesis

The final semester will focus on practical application and the completion of a thesis or capstone project. Students will engage in:

- **Internship/Practical Experience:** A hands-on internship with a relevant organization to apply learned skills in a real-world setting.
- **Thesis/Capstone Project:** A comprehensive project that demonstrates the application of project management principles in a sustainable context, culminating in a formal presentation.

Career Opportunities

Graduates of the Master's Degree in Sustainable Project Management will be well-prepared for a variety of career paths, including:

- Project Manager in NGOs and international organizations
- Consultant for sustainability initiatives
- Program Director for community development projects construction project manager
- Manager in corporate social responsibility (CSR) departments
- Researcher or academic in project management and sustainability

Admission Requirements

To apply for the program, candidates must meet the following criteria:

- A Bachelor's degree in a relevant field (e.g., Management, Environmental Science, IT, Health Sciences, Education, Engineering, Science, Arts) with a minimum second division.
- Relevant work experience or volunteer hours in project management or related fields is preferred.
- Submission of a statement of purpose, curriculum vitae, and two letters of recommendation.

3. **Master's in Naturopathy and Health Care Professional**

Diploma Program in Naturopathy and Health Care Professional, aimed at training professionals in holistic health practices that integrate modern and traditional medicine. This program will prepare graduates to address health issues through natural therapies, emphasizing preventive care and wellness.

Program Overview

- **Duration:** 2 years (4 semesters)
- **Delivery Mode:** Blended learning (on-campus and online components)

Curriculum Structure

Semester 1: Core Courses

The first semester will introduce foundational concepts in naturopathy and holistic health. Core courses will include:

- **Principles of Naturopathy:** Overview of naturopathic philosophy and principles.
- **Human Anatomy and Physiology:** Understanding the human body systems and their functions.
- **Nutrition and Dietary Therapy:** Role of nutrition in health and disease management.
- **Herbal Medicine:** Study of medicinal plants and their therapeutic applications.

Semester 2: Advanced Naturopathic Practices

The second semester will focus on advanced practices and methodologies in naturopathy:

- **Clinical Naturopathy:** Techniques for assessing and treating patients using naturopathic methods.
- **Detoxification and Cleansing Therapies:** Methods for detoxifying the body and promoting health.
- **Mind-Body Medicine:** Exploring the connection between mental and physical health.
- **Research Methodology:** Introduction to research design and methods specific to naturopathic studies.

Semester 3: Specialization Electives

Students will choose electives based on their interests and career goals. Elective options may include:

- **Homeopathy:** Principles and practices of homeopathic medicine.
- **Acupuncture and Traditional Chinese Medicine:** Techniques and theories behind acupuncture and TCM.
- **Integrative Medicine:** Combining conventional and alternative therapies for patient care.
- **Pediatric Naturopathy:** Approaches to treating children with naturopathic methods.

Semester 4: Practical Experience and Thesis

The final semester will focus on practical application and the completion of a thesis or capstone project:

- **Clinical Internship:** Hands-on experience in a clinical setting, applying naturopathic

principles under supervision.

- **Thesis/Capstone Project:** A research project that addresses a specific issue in naturopathy, culminating in a formal presentation.

Career Opportunities

Graduates of the Master's Degree in Naturopathy will be qualified to pursue various career paths, including:

- Clinical Naturopath
- Wellness Consultant
- Herbal Medicine Practitioner
- Health Educator
- Researcher in Natural Health Sciences

Admission Requirements

To enroll in the program, candidates must meet the following criteria:

- A Bachelor's degree in a relevant field (e.g., Health Sciences, Biology, Nutrition) with a minimum second division.
- Relevant work experience or volunteer hours in health or wellness settings is preferred.
- Submission of a statement of purpose, curriculum vitae, and two letters of recommendation.
- By launching this Master's Degree in Naturopathy, Madhesh University aims to contribute to the growing field of natural health and wellness, preparing graduates to make a positive impact in their communities.

Faculty Development

- Recruit and retain highly qualified faculty members with strong academic and research credentials and monitor as Career Advancement Skim through policy intervention from registrar office.
- Provide regular training and professional development opportunities for faculty to enhance their teaching and research skills
- Encourage faculty participation in national and international conferences, workshops, and collaborations
- Collaborate with Reputed University to conduct joint faculty development program and offer PhD with national university.
- Collaborate community colleges of the province to uplift education quality by offering PhD with reputed university developing Madhesh university as study center.

Student-Centric Learning

- Adopt learner-centric approaches to create an engaging and interactive learning environment
- Implement continuous assessment systems (CAS) to monitor student progress and provide timely feedback
- Offer mentorship programs, career guidance, and soft-skill development workshops for students

- implement course implementation plan strict to calendar
- offer skill based modular courses in each semester
- Collaborate with industry partners and government agencies to secure placement and funding for research projects

Infrastructure and Resources

- Invest in state-of-the-art infrastructure, including modern classrooms, laboratories, and libraries
- Ensure adequate funding for software development, maintenance, and capacity building programs
- Leverage digital technologies to enhance teaching, learning, and administrative processes
- Quality Assurance and Accreditation
- Implement a robust quality assurance system to monitor and evaluate academic programs
- Ensure that all academic programs undergo regular accreditation and quality assurance audits
- Use the results of quality assurance assessments to drive continuous improvement in academic standards
- Community Engagement and Social Responsibility
- Collaborate with local communities to address their educational and developmental needs
- Engage in outreach activities, such as community service projects and awareness campaigns
- Foster a culture of social responsibility and environmental sustainability among students and faculty
- Foster a culture of Occupational Safety and Health through student clubs under faculty guidance

SECTION F

RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PLAN FOR MADHESH UNIVERSITY

To establish Madhesh University (MU) as a leading institution for research and innovation, a comprehensive plan is essential. This plan will focus on fostering a robust research culture, enhancing collaboration with industry, and promoting educational advancements in line with the vision of the university and society at large.

Specific Objectives

- 1. Promote a Research Culture:** Foster an environment that encourages faculty and students to engage in meaningful research that contributes to societal needs and technological advancements.
- b. Industry Collaboration:** Establish partnerships with local and international industries to ensure research is relevant and beneficial to the community and economy.
- c. Innovative Educational Programs:** Develop and implement career-directed educational programs focusing on innovative problem-solving in technology, and applied sciences.
- d. Research and Innovation Centers:** Create specialized centers for research in key areas such as medicine, tourism, Ayurveda, law, management, education, oriental philosophy, technology, and sustainable practices.
- e. Support for Entrepreneurship:** Encourage entrepreneurial initiatives among students and faculty through incubation centers and support programs as social learning management system in partnership with society.

Action Plan

1. Establishing a Research Culture

- **Induction of Research Teams:** Form research committees at both societal and departmental levels to promote collaboration and resource sharing among faculty and students in collaboration with different agencies.
- **Workshops and Training:** Conduct regular workshops to enhance research skills among faculty and students, focusing on proposal writing, research methodologies, and publication strategies.
- **Incentives for Research:** Implement a reward system for faculty and students who publish research papers and secure grants, fostering a competitive research environment.

2. Enhancing Industry Collaboration

- **Industry Advisory Board:** Create an advisory board comprising industry leaders to guide research directions and ensure alignment with market needs.
- **Internship and Placement Programs:** Develop strong internship programs that allow students to gain practical experience and contribute to ongoing research projects in collaboration with industries.
- **Joint Research Projects:** Initiate joint research projects with industries to address specific challenges, leveraging academic expertise to provide innovative solutions.

3. Developing Innovative Educational Programs

- **Curriculum Development:** Regularly update curricula to include emerging technologies and industry trends, ensuring that students are equipped with relevant skills.

- **Interdisciplinary Programs:** Promote interdisciplinary studies that combine Information Technology, Dairy technology, Sustainable human Actions, Sustainable Project Technology and social sciences to address complex societal issues.
- **Virtual Learning Environment:** Establish a virtual campus to facilitate online learning and collaboration, making education accessible to a wider audience through collaboration with national and international universities.

4. **Creating Research and Development Centers**

- **Centers of Excellence:** Establish specialized centers for research in medicine, tourism, Ayurveda, law, management, education, oriental philosophy, and technology, and sustainable practices, equipped with state-of-the-art facilities in partnership with different agencies.
- **Applied Research Focus:** Encourage applied research that addresses local and national challenges, with an emphasis on practical solutions that enhance productivity and income.
- **Community Engagement:** Implement community-based research initiatives that involve local stakeholders, ensuring that research outcomes benefit the community.

5. **Supporting Entrepreneurship**

- **Incubation Centers:** Create incubation centers to support student and faculty startups, providing mentorship, resources, and funding opportunities.
- **Entrepreneurship Education:** Integrate entrepreneurship education into the curriculum, encouraging students to develop their business ideas and innovations. Students club will be established in collaboration with society for operating social entrepreneurship as nonprofit organization.
- **Networking Opportunities:** Organize networking events and competitions to connect aspiring entrepreneurs with industry experts and investors.

Monitoring and Evaluation

- **Performance Metrics:** Establish key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure the success of research initiatives, including the number of publications, patents, and industry collaborations.
- **Regular Reviews:** Conduct annual reviews of the research and innovation plan to assess progress and make necessary adjustments based on feedback and changing circumstances.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Implement feedback mechanisms for faculty, students, and industry partners to continuously improve research initiatives and educational programs.

Impact Statement

Implement a robust monitoring and evaluation framework to assess the impact of the initiatives on community development and educational outcomes, allowing for continuous improvement and be the first university to publish impact of university on development.

Ranking of University

Ranking of university should be promoted through research. All research scholars should be requested to Register in following Social Research/ Research Indexing websites using MU official email address for ranking improvement:

- 1) ORCID-ID,
- 2) Google Scholar,

- 3) ResearchGate,
- 4) Elsevier's SSRN
- 5) Microsofts Academic,
- 6) www.semanticscholar.org.
- 7) BASE.

Journal Recognition

University should recognize Scholarly Publications standards annually in line with University Grants Commission guidelines:

- 1) MU Journals with Copyright in Authors & MU name
- 2) Journals Indexed in Crossref.
- 3) Journals Indexed in DOAJ
- 4) Journals Indexed in include Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE, OpenAire etc.
- 5) Patents (Nepali & International)

MU should follow Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) and try to be signature authority for Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA).

Case1: Unnath Tarai Abhiyan

In the context of Madhesh Province, the implementation of a project to serve as a model for fostering community development and enhancing educational outcomes should be initiated. This initiative can be tailored to the unique socio-economic landscape of Madhesh, focusing on the adoption of villages and schools, while promoting agricultural innovation and skill development.

Project Implementation: Madhesh Development Initiative

Vision and Objectives

- **Vision:** To empower communities in Madhesh Province through education, sustainable agricultural practices, and innovative solutions that foster self-reliance and economic growth.
- **Overall Objective:** To enhance the quality of life in Madhesh Province by integrating educational initiatives with community development, focusing on skill development, agricultural innovation, and social entrepreneurship.

Key Activities

1. Village and School Adoption Program

- **Orientation for New Students:** Organize programs where new students spend a few days in local villages to understand community needs and development prospects. This will also enhance their critical thinking and socialization skills.
- **Community Engagement:** Facilitate discussions and workshops with villagers to identify local challenges and development opportunities, fostering a sense of ownership and collaboration.

2. Social Entrepreneurship Initiatives

- **Non-Profit Agricultural Company:** Establish a non-profit company focused on agricultural production, employing local youth and school dropouts. This initiative will promote self-employment and skill development.
- **Hi-Tech Nursery Management:** Develop hi-tech nurseries for the propagation of high-quality

seedlings, incorporating modern agricultural techniques and providing training to local farmers.

3. Livestock and Crop Improvement

Genetic Improvement Programs: Implement programs for the genetic improvement of livestock herds such as artificial intercourse, enhancing productivity and income for local farmers.

4. Capacity Building and Skill Development

- **Training Programs:** Offer training on effective custom hiring systems, agricultural insurance, and subsidies to raise awareness and empower local farmers.
- **Establishment of Agricultural Development Centers:** Create university-affiliated agricultural development centers to promote collective management production systems and support local farmers.

5. Technical Support and Organic Farming

- **24-Hour Technical Support:** Provide continuous technical support to farmers, helping them adopt organic farming practices and improve their productivity in collaboration with Associations and Nepal Agriculture Research Council.
- **Organic Fertilizer Production:** Establish facilities for the production of organic fertilizers, promoting sustainable agricultural practices and reducing dependency on chemical inputs.

Project Benefits

- **Research Centers:** Establish dedicated research centers focusing on local issues such as agriculture, health, and sustainable development. This aligns with the university's commitment to community-oriented research.
- **Funding and Grants:** Seek partnerships with government bodies, NGOs, and international organizations to secure funding for research projects. Create internal grant programs to support faculty and student research.
- **Collaboration:** Foster collaborations with other universities and research institutions both nationally and internationally to enhance research output and visibility.
- **Outreach Programs:** Develop outreach initiatives that engage local communities, focusing on education, health, and sustainable practices. This could include workshops, seminars, and community service projects.
- **Skill Development:** Offer vocational training programs tailored to the needs of the local population, enhancing employability and addressing local economic challenges.
- **Cultural Integration:** Incorporate local culture and languages into the curriculum and community programs, ensuring that education is relevant and accessible to all segments of the population.

Case 2: Catchment Management

This proposal outlines a strategic initiative to adopt schools within the university's catchment area, aiming to enhance educational outcomes and establish community learning centers that facilitate skill transfer to learners in the society. By leveraging the university's resources and expertise, we seek to create a sustainable model for educational enhancement and community engagement using ecological system theory.

Objectives

1. **Enhance Educational Quality:** Improve the quality of education in adopted schools by providing access to resources, training, and support from MU faculty and students.
2. **Establish Community Learning Centers:** Create centers that offer skill development programs, vocational training, and lifelong learning opportunities for community members.
3. **Foster Collaboration:** Build partnerships with local schools, community organizations, and stakeholders to ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of educational initiatives.
4. **Promote Lifelong Learning:** Encourage continuous learning and skill development among community members, focusing on relevant skills that align with local economic needs.

Proposed Activities

1. School Adoption Program

- a. **Identification of Schools:** Conduct a needs assessment to identify schools in the catchment area that would benefit from collaboration with MU.
- b. **Resource Allocation:** Allocate resources, including educational materials, technology, and faculty support, to enhance the educational environment in adopted schools.
- c. **Training for Educators:** Provide professional development workshops for teachers in adopted schools, focusing on innovative teaching methods, curriculum development, and student engagement strategies.

2. Establishment of Community Learning Centers

- a. **Location and Infrastructure:** Identify suitable locations for community learning centers within the catchment area, ensuring accessibility for community members.
- b. **Program Development:** Develop a range of programs offered at the learning centers, including vocational training, computer literacy, entrepreneurship, and life skills workshops.
- c. **Collaboration with Local Organizations:** Partner with local NGOs and community organizations to deliver programs that address specific community needs and interests.

3. Student Engagement and Involvement

- a. **Volunteer Opportunities:** Encourage MU students to participate as volunteers in the school adoption and community learning center initiatives, providing them with hands-on experience in community engagement.
- b. **Mentorship Programs:** Establish mentorship programs where MU students can mentor school students, fostering academic support and personal development.

4. Monitoring and Evaluation

- a. **Data Collection:** Implement a system for collecting data on the impact of the school adoption program and community learning centers, including student performance, attendance, and community participation.
- b. **Feedback Mechanisms:** Create feedback mechanisms for students, educators, and community members to assess the effectiveness of programs and identify areas for improvement.
- c. **Regular Reporting:** Prepare regular reports on the progress of the initiatives, sharing outcomes with stakeholders and making adjustments as needed.

Conclusion of the Session

By implementing this comprehensive research and innovation plan, Madhesh University can position itself as a leader in technological education and research in Nepal. This plan not only aligns with the university's vision but also addresses the pressing needs of the local community and economy. Through a focus on collaboration, entrepreneurship, and applied research, MU will contribute significantly to the socio-economic development of Madhesh Province and the nation as a whole.

SECTION G

PLACEMENT PLAN FOR STUDENTS AT MADHESH UNIVERSITY

The following comprehensive plan to ensure the successful placement of our graduates:

1. Team Building and Mentorship

- Establish a dedicated Placement Cell to coordinate all placement-related activities.
- Assign faculty mentors to guide and support students throughout their placement journey.
- Encourage students to form study groups and project teams to foster collaboration and teamwork.

2. Industry Exposure and Networking

- Organize regular industry visits, guest lectures, and workshops to expose students to real-world challenges and best practices in robotics.
- Facilitate internship opportunities for students to gain practical experience and build professional networks.
- Encourage participation in national and international competitions and hackathons.

3. Skill Development and Training

- Conduct skill assessments to identify areas for improvement and tailor training programs accordingly.
- Offer workshops and training sessions on in-demand skills such as Software and hardware.
- Provide training on soft skills; resume writing, and interview techniques to enhance employability.

4. Corporate Engagement and Partnerships

- Establish strong relationships with leading companies, startups, and research organizations.
- Organize campus recruitment drives, job fairs, and company presentations to connect students with potential employers.
- Collaborate with industry partners to design industry-relevant curricula and projects.

5. Internship and Job Placement

- Facilitate internship opportunities for students to gain practical experience and build professional networks.
- Maintain a database of potential employers and job openings in the industry.
- Provide guidance and support to students during the job application and interview process.
- Organize mock interviews and practice sessions to help students prepare for placements.

6. Alumni Engagement and Mentorship

- Engage with successful alumni working in the industry to provide mentorship and guidance to current students.
- Organize alumni networking events and workshops to foster a strong alumni community.
- Encourage alumni to participate in campus recruitment drives and share their experiences with students.

7. Continuous Improvement and Feedback

- Regularly monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the placement plan.
- Gather feedback from students, faculty, and industry partners to identify areas for improvement.
- Incorporate best practices and innovative strategies to enhance the placement process continuously.
- By implementing this comprehensive placement plan, Madhesh University aims to ensure the successful placement of our graduates in leading organizations, contributing to the growth and development of the industry in Nepal and beyond.

Figure 1: Possible path for academic excellence of Madhesh University

Figure 1 shows the social learning management system for community involvement, student engagement and research based teaching.

SECTION H CONCLUSION

With a profound commitment to competition-based education and the concept of a university, MU is dedicated to continuously raising the bar in higher education standards. As the university takes its first steps towards its mission, it seeks to create a learner-centric educational ecosystem and strives to be at the forefront of higher education institutions in the region. MU is the founding member of the Regional Centre of Expertise (RCE) for Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) established in 2023 in Nepal. This affiliation has led MU to conceptualize environment sensitivity with less carbon emission as envisioned by the Nepal Government from the very beginning. The university aims to focus on life-skill and sustained livelihood-based courses through culture-friendly pedagogy, making it a unique institution with special features to intervene in higher education as incorporated by the Province Government of Madhesh.

The introduction of new academic programs, such as the Master's Degree in Sustainable Humanitarian Action and Bachelor's programs in Medical Technology and Clinical Research reflects our commitment to addressing the evolving needs of the community and the job market. By collaborating with relevant health councils and professional associations, we ensure that our curriculum meets industry standards and prepares students for successful careers. Research and innovation are central to our mission at MU. By prioritizing applied research initiatives that tackle local and regional challenges, we aim to establish partnerships with industry stakeholders that will facilitate impactful projects in applied sciences and sustainable development. This focus on research not only enhances the academic reputation of the university but also contributes to the broader goal of societal advancement. Recognizing the importance of student engagement and support, we are implementing comprehensive systems that include mentorship programs, career counseling, and skill development workshops. These initiatives are designed to enhance student employability and ensure that graduates are well-prepared to enter the workforce. Furthermore, our commitment to community outreach will strengthen our ties with local organizations, promoting health awareness and sustainable practices that benefit the community. Infrastructure development is another critical area of focus. By investing in upgrading our facilities and resources, including libraries, laboratories, and technological infrastructure, we will provide students and faculty with the tools necessary for success. A robust quality assurance framework will be established to continuously monitor and improve our academic programs, ensuring compliance with national and international educational standards. As we move forward, Madhesh University is poised to make significant strides in the coming years. Our focus on academic excellence, community service, and research innovation will position us as a leader in higher education within Madhesh Province. With the unwavering support of our faculty, staff, and stakeholders, we are confident in our ability to achieve these objectives and fulfill our mission of nurturing skilled professionals who will contribute to the development of our region and nation.

The strategic initiatives outlined in this paper are not merely goals but a commitment to creating a transformative educational experience at Madhesh University. By embracing innovation, fostering collaboration, and prioritizing the needs of our students and community, we will cultivate an academic environment that not only meets the challenges of today but also anticipates the opportunities of tomorrow. Together, we will build a prosperous future for Madhesh Province and its people, ensuring that education remains a powerful catalyst for change and development.

Limitations; As per the notice, Work plan was asked to be submitted for which specific timeline, resource allocations, verifiable indicators should be given as logical framework analysis, however, the research is broadly prepared as vision paper due to lack of information available.

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Annex-1

Table 1: Academic Departments Functional in the Institution

SN	Name of the Department	Faculty/Institute
1.	Department of BA.LLB	Faculty of Management
2.	Department of BPAM	

Table 2 Present Status of Student Enrollment should be studied.

Level	Program	No. of Students Per Semester										Total
		1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	
Bachelor's	BA. LLB											
	BPAM											
Total												

Table 3 Regional Profile of the Student (2080)

No. of Enrollment	Bachelor's		
	M	F	T
From the same district where the institution is located			
From other districts			
From SAARC Countries			
Total			

Table 4: Pass Rate of last years**Yearly System**

Program	Year	No. of Students Enrolled	Exam Appeared	No. of Students Passed	Pass %
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Program	Batch	Semester	No. of Students Enrolled	Exam Appeared	No. of Students Passed	Pass %
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Table 5: Program-wise Completion (graduation) and Drop-out rates of students for the last years.

Program (A)	Year of Enrolment (B)	Enrolment Number (C)	Final Year / Semester Examination (D)	Number of Students Appeared in Final Year / Semester Examination (only regular) (E)	Completion Number (include only regularly completing the program) (F)	Completion % = Graduate within postulated time (Cohort Year) / Enrolment of Cohort year *100 (F/C)*100	Drop-out % = Appeared in the Final semester or Year exam / Enrolment number of Cohort Year =100-(E/C*100)
BHM							
BIM							

Table 6: Human Resources Available in the Institution

Category	Number
Full Time Faculty Members	
Part Time Faculty Members	
Visiting/Guest Faculty Members	
Non-teaching Staffs	

Table 7: Details of the Faculty Members

SN	Designation of the Faculties	No. of the Faculties by Nature/Type		
		Full Time	Part Time	Visiting
1	Professor			
2	Reader/Associate Professor			
3	Lecturer/Asst. Professor			
4	Teaching Assistant/Instructor			
Total				

Table 8: Other Details of the Faculty Members (full time)

Academic Qualification	No. of Faculties
Post Doc.	
PhD	
M. Phil	
Master's	
Bachelor's	
Experience (in Yrs)	No. of Faculties
More than 20 years	
15 to 20 years	
10 to 15 years	
5 to 10 years	
Less than 5 years	

Table 9: Details of the Non-teaching Staff

Particulars	Distribution of Staff by Gender		
	Male	Female	Total
Officers			
Assistants			
Support/help staff			
Technical Staff			
Total			

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